

ETYMOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE TERMS IRRIGATION AND LAND RECLAMATION IN THE EXPLANATORY DICTIONARIES OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Etymological research has long been the focus of particular attention among linguists. Such studies involve the analysis of a word's linguistic affiliation, the language in which it first appeared during the period of its early usage, its original meaning, as well as the specific features of its semantic development. This article emphasizes the necessity of lexicographic research in the etymological analysis of the terms "irrigation" and "melioration". Special importance is attached to explanatory and etymological dictionaries, language corpora, and thesauruses in this context.

Keywords: irrigation, land reclamation, history of terms, explanatory dictionaries, etymological analysis, proprietary layer, layer of appropriation

Аннотация

Этимологик таҳлиллار даврлар оша тилшунослар диққат марказида бўлган тадқиқотлар ҳисобланади. Ушбу тадқиқот со'знинг қaysи тилга мансублиги, ilk iste'molga кирган даврлардаyoq қaysи тилда paydo бўлганлиги, dastlab қандаy tushuncha ifodalaganлиги, ma'no taraqqoyotining xususiyatlarini таҳлилga tortadi. Mazkur maqolada irrigatsiya va melioratsiya terminlari etimologik таҳлилларида leksikografik izlanishlar zarurligi, bunda, ayniqsa, izohli lug'atlar, etimologik lug'atlar, til korpuslari, shuningdek tezaruslar muhim o'rin tutishi bayon etilgan.

Калит со'злар: Irrigatsiya, melioratsiya, terminlar tarixi, izohli lug'atlar, etimologik таҳлил, o'z qatlam, o'zlashma qatlam

Аннотация

Этимологические исследования на протяжении времени являются объектом особого внимания лингвистов. В рамках таких исследований анализируется языковая принадлежность слова, язык его возникновения ещё в период раннего употребления, первоначальное значение, а также особенности развития его семантики. В данной статье подчёркивается необходимость лексикографических исследований в этимологическом анализе терминов «иригация» и «мелиорация». При этом особое значение придаётся толковым и этимологическим словарям, языковым корпусам, а также тезаурусам.

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Ключевые слова: ирригация, мелиорация земель, история терминов, толковые словари, этимологический анализ, собственный слой, слой присвоения

Etymology is considered one of the most important branches of linguistics. The origin and formation of words, phrases, and other linguistic units have always been at the center of attention for specialists. Etymological research also plays a crucial role in identifying the differences between a word's original meaning and the meaning it acquires as a result of progress and development. Since etymological studies focus on analyzing the peculiarities of semantic development, the language to which a word belongs, and the concept it was originally intended to express, lexicographic research is equally essential. A significant role in this process is played by etymological dictionaries, explanatory dictionaries, language corpora, and thesauruses. This article emphasizes the necessity of lexicographic research in the etymological analysis of the terms "*irrigation*" and "*melioration*", with particular importance given to explanatory dictionaries, etymological dictionaries, language corpora, and thesauruses.

Research dedicated to the etymological description of units within a specific lexico-semantic group enables the proper use of linguistic units in particular speech situations. Accurate systematization of terminological units is also essential for confirming their connection to concepts and for eliminating polyfunctionality and synonymy in terminology. The study of the etymological features of the terms *irrigation* and *melioration* has been partially conducted within Uzbek linguistics. Specifically, X. Jabbarov performed an etymological analysis of agricultural terminology. In his examination of the lexeme "*dehqon*" (peasant), the scholar notes that research related to its origin was carried out not only by linguists but also by historians, geographers, scholars of antiquity, and Hellenists, emphasizing that this lexeme has undergone significant semantic expansion compared to its original state[1:45]. Indeed, in its original meaning, the lexeme "*dehqon*" would not have been distinguished as a term in the field of irrigation and land reclamation. However, in modern explanatory dictionaries, this lexeme is defined as "asosiy kasbi yerga ishlov berish, ekin ekishdan iborat bo'lgan kishi"[2:816–817], which is presented in a dictionary entry revealing this meaning. In this regard, the analysis of the etymological features of lexical units in this field allows for the clarification of their semantic characteristics.

The majority of the terms in the fields of irrigation and land reclamation consist of Turkic words. The formation of industry-specific terms related to the

Turkic language can be explained by the fact that the peoples who inhabited the territory of our country have been engaged in agriculture since the times before our era [3:229]. Later, when cultural interaction with agriculture began, terms representing concepts related to water structures, the names of cultivated plants, and methods of land cultivation created by humanity started to enrich our lexicon. The Turkic layer constitutes the main part of the native linguistic stratum. The lexemes related to the fields of irrigation and reclamation, listed below, belong to the Turkic stratum: for example, *aralashma* (mixture), *ariq* (canal), *arpa* (barley), *balchiq* (clay), *balchiqli* (muddy), *balchiqlik* (muddy land), *bug'doy* (wheat), *botqoq* (swamp), *botqoqlanish* (swamping), *botqoqli* (swampy), *botqoqlik* (swampiness), *bulut* (cloud), *buloq* (spring), *burg'i* (drill), *burg'ilamoq* (to drill), *bug'* (steam), *bug'lanish* (evaporation), *urug'* (seed), *ildiz* (root), *ekin* (crop), *yer* (land), *tuproq* (soil), *suv* (water), *suvloq* (wet), *ko'l* (lake), *quduq* (well), *o'zan* (bed), *dengiz* (sea), *irmoq* (stream), *ketmon* (hoe), *toshqin* (flood), *ko'tarma* (embankment), *egat* (ditch), *soy* (brook). In the process of identifying the indigenous layer of terms related to irrigation and land reclamation, we can say that the etymological data provided in explanatory dictionaries serve as the primary indicators. At the same time, the specific phonetic features of common Turkic words (such as the words being predominantly monosyllabic or disyllabic; the absence of a sequence of consonants at the end of a word; the full opening of the first syllable in disyllabic words; the second syllable not beginning with a vowel; and stress falling on the final syllable, among others) and semantic characteristics (such as the polysemy of most lexemes)[4] also simplify the process. The etymological data used to identify lexemes were also based on the information provided in Sh.Rahmatullayev's "Etymological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" (2000), which is considered a significant source in Uzbek linguistics. As mentioned, etymological data is the result of research conducted to determine the original form and meaning of words. The "ariq" lexeme, included in the list of Turkic and Uzbek words above, is found in the first volume of Sh. Rahmatullaev's dictionary of Turkic words and is explained as follows: "kichik oqin suv yo'li. Bu ot asli qadimgi turkiy tildagi "oq" ma'nosini anglatgan a:p- fe'lidan -ық qo'shimchasi bilan yasalgan. Keyinroq a: unlisining cho'ziqlik belgisi yo'qolgan"[5:34]. Such etymological analyses prove that words currently interpreted as root words were historically formed through derivation. For example, the information that the lexeme "ariq" which is considered a root word today, is derived from the verb "oqmoq" (to flow) has

been obtained through etymological analysis. This data demonstrates that the lexeme is directly related to the field of irrigation and reclamation.

Among the Uzbek irrigation and reclamation terms, loanwords also form a significant part. In particular, the influence of the Persian-Tajik language has been most prominent at the lexical level. Lexical items borrowed from this language, such as *marza*, *maydon*, *girdob*, *dara*, *daryo*, *dasta*, *dasht*, *dahyak*, *dehqon*, *jo'yak*, *joybon*, *nov*, *nishob*, *sho'rxok*, *damba*, *sardoba*, *zamin*, *zamindor*, *zang*, *zarang*, *kanora*, *paykal*, etc., have firmly taken their place in the modern Uzbek language lexicon. The Uzbek people use these lexical units in their speech processes as part of their lexical heritage. In the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language, a special note (*f.*) is made for the units borrowed from the Persian-Tajik language. This etymological information plays a key role in identifying the units from the Persian-Tajik language in the Uzbek irrigation and reclamation terminology system. Most of the lexical items borrowed from the Persian-Tajik language have also acquired the characteristic of polysemy. This indicates that these lexical units have been part of the Uzbek lexicon for a long time. For example, the two meanings of the lexeme *marza* are explained in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language.

“MARZA [*f.* – chegara, sarhad; o'lka; egat] q.x. 1 Ekinzor yoki uning bir bo'lagini boshqa bo'lakdan ajratish uchun ma'lum balandlikda tuproq uyib hosil qilingan chegara; egat, yo'l.

2 Ariq sirti; pushta”[6:117-118]

The lexeme *marza*, which we are analyzing, has etymological meanings such as “*chegara, sarhad; o'lka; egat*” as recorded in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language. However, it should be noted here that the meaning of *o'lka* is no longer preserved in the modern Uzbek language. The abbreviation “*q.x*” (agriculture) used in the dictionary entry indicates that the lexeme is related to the field of agriculture. Since irrigation and reclamation are integral parts of agriculture, this connection is significant. Similarly, another term, *girdob*, was formed in the Persian-Tajik language through compounding and was borrowed into Uzbek in this form. The Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language provides four definitions for *girdob*, but only one of them can be included within the system of irrigation and reclamation terminology.

The etymological information provided for this lexeme in the *Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language* is as follows: “*suv uyurmasi, kamar, o'pqn*”[7:231]

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The presence of Arabic words in the Uzbek irrigation and melioration terminology system has been identified through the analysis of dictionaries and other linguistic sources. Arabic loanwords in the Uzbek language, like those from Persian-Tajik, have long been an integral part of the nation's cultural heritage. As a result, lexical units of Arabic origin are actively used in Uzbek speech. Lexemes such as *anhor*, *sel*, *bahr*, *vodiy*, *nahr*, *sohil*, *hovuz*, *maydon*, *hashar*, *tanob*, *nav*, *samum*, *sath*, *sahro*, *sel*, *sohil*, *modda*, etc., which are actively used in the irrigation and melioration terminology system, support this argument. It is difficult to find a speaker of Uzbek who does not understand these words. For instance, the Arabic lexeme *sel* has six meanings in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. Two of these meanings are directly related to the field of irrigation and melioration. However, the etymological meaning of the word shows a difference from its current meaning: “oqim; soy, anhor, jilg’a”[8:588].

The development of the fields of irrigation and land reclamation (melioration) in Uzbekistan is closely linked to the historical period of the Soviet era, particularly with the introduction of technology into agriculture and the expansion of new arable lands. As a result, as in many other fields, the number of Russian-origin terms in the irrigation and melioration sector increased significantly. However, it is important to note that not all borrowings that entered the Uzbek language through Russian originated in Russian itself — many of them were originally borrowed by the Russian language from other languages before being adopted into Uzbek via Russian. Commonly used lexemes in this field include *ammiak* (*ammonia*), *selitra* (*saltpeter*), *traktor* (*tractor*), *kaliy* (*potassium*), *irrigatsiya* (*irrigation*), *melioratsiya* (*melioration*), *mineralogiya* (*mineralogy*), *gidrotexnik* (*hydrotechnician*), *kolxoz* (*collective farm*), *pudratchi* (*contractor*), *lotok* (*channel tray*), *irrigator*, *vodokachka* (*water pump*), *kanal* (*canal*), *nasos* (*pump*), *vodokanal* (*waterworks*), *drenaj* (*drainage*), and *truba* (*pipe*).

In recent years, the process of borrowing words from European languages into Uzbek has no longer required the intermediary role of the Russian language. At present, the adoption of new terms into Uzbek occurs directly, and this process also applies to the terminology of the irrigation and land reclamation (melioration) sector. For instance, the lexeme *marker*, used in the field of irrigation and melioration, etymologically traces back to the French word *marqueur*. In French, this lexeme conveys the meanings of “to mark” or “to place a sign.” In contemporary Uzbek, as a specialized term in irrigation and melioration, *marker* refers to a “Egat olish va ekin ekish uchun reja chizig’i

tortuvchi asbob; xatkash” [6:113]. This example reflects the emergence of new approaches within the process of word adoption in the Uzbek language.

The etymological analysis of Uzbek terminology in the field of irrigation and land reclamation reveals that native lexical layers play a leading role within the system. This can be explained by the fact that agriculture has historically been a dominant sector in the life of the Uzbek people for many centuries. In the process of adopting terminology specific to this field, various factors have held primary influence. For example, in the case of borrowing from Russian and Arabic, language policy implemented in the country was elevated to a decisive factor. Meanwhile, in the case of borrowing from the Tajik language, the close neighborhood relations between the two peoples served as the primary factor facilitating the exchange.

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